

TRANSLATION PECULIARITIES OF LAW TERMS

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Annotation: This thesis explores the unique challenges faced by translators working within legal contexts, including issues of equivalence, cultural differences, and the impact of legal systems on translation practices, the role of technology and resources available to legal translators, the importance of context in interpreting legal texts, strategies for effective legal translation.

Key words: legal translation, linguistic proficiency, legal systems, terminology, equivalence, cultural differences, contextual interpretation, translation strategies.

Introduction:

Legal translation is a specialized field that demands a nuanced understanding of both the source and target legal systems, as well as the intricate cultural contexts in which these systems operate. One of the primary challenges in legal translation arises from the variability inherent in different legal systems, particularly between common law and civil law jurisdictions. For instance, terms such as "tort" or "contract" may have precise definitions within common law frameworks but may not possess direct counterparts in civil law systems, where the focus may be on codified statutes rather than case law precedents. This discrepancy necessitates a careful consideration of functional equivalents,

compelling translators to either find terms that convey similar legal concepts or to provide expansive explanations that clarify the intended meaning for the target audience. Thus, the translator's role extends beyond mere linguistic conversion; it encompasses a deep engagement with the legal principles underlying the terms being translated.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Moreover, the contextual understanding of legal terminology is paramount in ensuring accurate translations. Legal terms often carry specific meanings that can vary significantly based on their usage within particular contexts. For example, the term "equity" might refer to a body of law in one context while denoting fairness in another. This multiplicity of meanings requires translators to possess not only linguistic proficiency but also a robust understanding of legal doctrines and practices relevant to both the source and target languages. In many cases, legal concepts have evolved through judicial interpretation, further complicating their translation. Consequently, translators must navigate these complexities with precision, ensuring that their choices reflect not only the letter of the law but also its spirit.

Here are additional examples that illustrate the complexities of legal translation across different contexts:

1. Contract Law

The term "indemnity" in common law jurisdictions often refers to a contractual agreement where one party agrees to compensate another for certain damages or losses. In civil law jurisdictions, the equivalent might be "garantie,"

but it may not carry the same implications regarding liability and compensation. The translator must clarify whether "indemnity" refers to a broad concept of compensation or a specific legal obligation, potentially requiring an explanatory note.

2. Corporate Law

"Shareholder" vs. "stakeholder" can create confusion. While shareholders own shares in a company, stakeholders include anyone affected by the company's operations, including employees and customers. Translators must clarify these distinctions to avoid conflating the two terms, especially in corporate governance documents.

3. International Law

Terms like "sovereignty" can have varied interpretations depending on the political context. In some cultures, it may emphasize territorial integrity, while in others, it may focus on self-determination. The translator must consider the political implications of the term in the target culture, ensuring that the translation reflects the intended meaning without bias.

Cultural nuances play a critical role in legal translation, influencing how legal concepts are perceived and understood across different societies. The legal culture within a jurisdiction can shape public attitudes toward terms like "justice," "due process," or "rights," which may carry distinct connotations depending on historical and social contexts. For instance, concepts of justice in common law countries may emphasize adversarial proceedings, while civil law jurisdictions may prioritize inquisitorial processes. Such differences necessitate a careful approach

to translation, as failing to account for these cultural dimensions can result in misinterpretations that undermine the intended message. Additionally, public perception of legal terms can affect their translation; what is considered a standard term in one culture may evoke entirely different associations in another.

Results:

The technical nature of legal language further complicates the translation process. Legal texts are characterized by their precision and formality, requiring translators to maintain this level of specificity to avoid ambiguity. Legal jargon, often laden with technicalities, may not have direct translations in other languages, thereby necessitating either descriptive translations or footnotes for clarification. For instance, terms such as "power of attorney" must be translated in a way that conveys their legal function accurately within the target jurisdiction's framework. In some cases, loanwords are employed—terms borrowed directly from one language into another—particularly in international law contexts where certain concepts are universally recognized yet linguistically distinct.

Additionally, the distinction between legislative texts and judicial decisions presents unique challenges for translators. Statutory language often adheres to a formal structure and specific phrasing that must be preserved to maintain legal integrity during translation. Conversely, judicial opinions may require a more interpretative approach due to the subjective nature of judicial reasoning and the potential for varying interpretations of legal principles. The translator must navigate these differences skillfully, ensuring that the translated text reflects both the original intent and the applicable legal standards.

Discussion:

Consistency in terminology is another critical aspect of effective legal translation. Maintaining uniformity throughout a document is essential, especially in lengthy legal texts where repeated terms may arise. Developing a glossary of key terms can be an invaluable resource for ensuring that terminology remains consistent across various sections of a document. Furthermore, when translating documents that reference precedents or specific cases, it is crucial for translators to accurately convey these references and ensure they are understood within the context of the target jurisdiction's legal framework.

Finally, professional standards play an integral role in the field of legal translation. Many jurisdictions require legal translators to possess specific qualifications or certifications to ensure reliability and accuracy in their work. Adherence to ethical considerations is also paramount; translators must maintain confidentiality regarding sensitive information and approach their work with impartiality to uphold the integrity of the legal profession.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, translating legal terms is a multifaceted endeavor that requires not only linguistic skill but also an intricate understanding of legal principles, cultural contexts, and ethical standards. The complexities involved in navigating different legal systems, contextual nuances, and technical language underscore the importance of specialized knowledge in this field. As globalization continues to blur jurisdictional boundaries, the demand for skilled legal translators will undoubtedly grow, highlighting the need for ongoing education and professional development within this vital discipline.

References:

- 1.** Kinderknekht A.S. The problem of legal terminology translation // Scientific Notes of Orel State University. 2013.
- 2.** Shirobokova L.P. Legal texts: grammatical-typological research. Summary Dis., Candidate of Philology. Moscow, 2007.
- 3.** Bobrova, N. E., Lebedev, A. V. Peculiarities of the English Legal Text Discourse: The issues of Interpretation and Translatability. Journal of History Culture and Art Research, 2020.
- 4.** Faber, P. & Reimerink, A. Framing terminology in legal translation. International Journal of Legal Discourse, 2019.